

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15846220

Utilization Of Electronic Information Resources By Students Of Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic, Kazaure

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ABSTRACT

This research seek to investigate and explore the factors that are responsible for underutilization of electronic information resources by student in Hussaini Adamu federal Polytechnic Kazaure, Jigawa state. The research adopted descriptive survey research, using quantitative method to collect data because it is a suitable and efficient way of studying large populations. The population of the study cover all ND and HND Students, a proportionate random sampling was used to represent the entire population which is one of the probability sampling techniques, to ensure proportional representative in the sample size, Research Advisor's table (2006) was use to recruit 200 participants using krejice and Morgan formula. A personally developed Questionnaire using three (3) points likert scale technique was developed as an instrument for data collection and administered by the researchers. The data were collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics where frequency tables, percentages, means and standard deviation was used. The findings indicate that although electronic information resources such as e-books, databases, and internet services are available within the institution's library, their utilization by students remains suboptimal. E-books, databases, and internet services emerged as the most frequently accessed resources, primarily for academic purposes such as completing assignments, conducting research, and other scholarly activities. Despite the moderate benefits reported by the students, their usage patterns revealed a tendency to access these resources on a bi-weekly basis. Poor internet connectivity, unstable electricity supply, information overload, and limited access to available resources were identified as the challenges significantly hinder students from fully benefiting from the electronic resources provided. It is recommended that the polytechnic administration prioritize investment in ICT infrastructure, enhance internet connectivity, and organize regular training sessions aimed at building students' information literacy skills. Additionally, awareness campaigns should be conducted to promote the availability and advantages of electronic information resources.

Keywords: Utilization, Electronic Information resources, Polytechnic library

1.0 INTRODUCTION

According to Sola *et. al.*, (2016), the use of ICT has the potential to radically alter present social structure and mode of operation, and this social change will in turn force educational institutions to react and change as well. With respect to the role of technology in higher education, Shields (2000) broke down the socio-technological movements into three stages. The first stage, the first personal computing movement of the early to mid –1980s spawned the second, the networking of the late 1980s to mid-1990s; the latter, in turn envisions the rise of virtual universities during the 2000s (Rosemberg, 2001). What is interesting about the third movement is that some of the advocates of virtual education believe that the traditional model of campus-based teaching, learning and scholarship must adapt to new technological realities, (for example the Internet, digital libraries, broad band multimedia capabilities, etc) or the proponents of distance learning believe that an ICT driven revolution can make higher education more affordable and more acceptable (Vikky and Shyamu 2022).

Most importantly, ICT significantly changes the way learning is conducted with the increase of information and communication technologies for instructional design, delivery and technology supported learning Barclay (2001). With the development of information technology, electronic resources are now available for use in libraries. New trends in the computer technology are allowing libraries to do things with more efficient and effective tools (Sola *et. al.*, 2016).

Based on the several literature reviewed by the researchers some countries especially developing countries such as Pakistan, India, and some African countries (like Nigeria, Ghana and Uganda) utilization of electronic information resources is bedevil by a number of challenges.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Several literature reviewed recently indicated that electronic information resources are present in Nigerian libraries especially academic libraries. Adetimirin (2019) noted that literature from Nigeria shows that academic libraries are investing in acquisition of electronic information resources to ensure academic success of their members.

Despite the amount of money invest in provision of such resources many students in some institution especially polytechnics are not benefitting maximally with this great opportunity base on the pilot study conducted by the researchers, this lead to underutilization or low level of usage of electronic information resources.

It is on this thrust, this research billed to investigate and explore the factors that lead to underutilization of such resources to students in some polytechnics by selecting a polytechnic library (Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure library) as the study area.

1.4 Objectives of the Research

The objectives of the research were to:

- 1) Find out the types of electronic information resources that are currently available for students in Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure
- 2) Evaluate the extent to which the students utilize the electronic information resources in the Polytechnic Library,
- 3) Find out the frequency of usage of electronic resources by the Students,
- 4) Find out the benefits being derived by the Student from the use of electronic information resources,
- 5) Ascertain the purpose for which the Students use the electronic resources
- 6) Explore the factors that hinder the use of electronic resources by students in the selected polytechnic library.

1.3 Research Question

The research seek to address the following questions

- 1) What type of electronic information resources are currently available for students in Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic main library?
- 2) What is the extent of utilizing electronic information resources by students in the selected polytechnic library?

- 3) What is the frequency of usage of electronic information resources by students in the Polytechnic library?
- 4) What are the benefits derived by the students from utilizing electronic information resources in the Polytechnic library?
- 5) What are the purpose of utilizing electronic information resources by students in the selected library?
- 6) What are the factors that hinder the utilization of electronic information resources by students in the selected library?

1.4 Significance of the research

It is hope that the study would go beyond finding solution on the low level of utilization of electronic information resources but make a significant contribution towards being proactive by the polytechnic management and polytechnic librarian in developing relevant ICT policies/strategies for effective and sustainable electronic collection development in Nigerian polytechnics.

The result of the study would be useful to all professional librarians, academic staff, polytechnic management and researchers to understand and appreciate the role of electronic information resources towards academic success of the students.

The result of the study would provide a recorded knowledge on the ideal academic library situation, it would be of empirical benefit to intending researchers as it will serve as a reference materials for those who may wish to undertake research in similar area. Soft copy of this work will be uploaded on the internet for academics, librarians, researchers and the general public to have access to it for information sharing will hard copy will be display in the library for consumption.

1.5 Scope and limitations

The geographical scope covered a selected polytechnic library in Jigawa State that is Hussaini Adamu federal polytechnic library. The content scope were basically on utilization of electronic information resources by students. The area covered by the study were: Types of electronic information resources available in the library, extent of utilization of the resources by the students, frequency of usage by students, purpose of utilization of electronic information resources by the students as well as the challenges that hinder the utilization of the resources by students in the selected library. The population scope was made up of all students both HND and ND Students in Hussaini Adamu federal Polytechnic Kazaure.

1.6 Definition of terms

Utilization: Utilization in this study refers to the usage of electronic information resources

Electronic information resources: Electronic information resources refers to any information stored in electronic format such as e-book, e-journals, online databases e.t.c using electronic resources to access its(computer or computer related facilities)

Polytechnic library: Is an academic library found in Polytechnics proving information services to their respective members that comprises students and staff (academic and non-academic staff) to support their teaching, learning and research.

Students: In this study students refers to individuals who are actively engaged in learning, both HND and ND Students in the polytechnic.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent research illustrates the growing importance of electronic information resources (EIRs) in academic libraries. Buba and Lawal (2023) explored the availability and utilization of electronic resources among undergraduates at the Federal University, Dutse, Nigeria. Their descriptive survey of 119 respondents showed moderate availability ($M=2.94$) and high utilization of e-books, e-journals, and databases, with issues such as erratic power and limited computer access still hindering use. Similarly, a study at Federal University Gashua reported that undergraduates rated availability, accessibility, and utilization of electronic information resources as "great extent", though inadequate ICT infrastructure remained a barrier . In Nigeria's University of Abuja, Okoro and colleagues (2022) found moderate usage of electronic information resources among 727 undergraduate students across Science and Arts faculties.

They recommended improved ICT funding, more database subscriptions, and skills training to boost engagement. Computer/digital literacy appears pivotal. Mabawonku et al. (2023) evaluated computer literacy’s impact on electronic information resources utilization among Babcock University Ogun state undergraduates. They found a strong positive correlation: students with higher ICT skills used more e-journals (90.7%) and e-theses (62.5%), and recommended ongoing training. In Rivers State University, digital literacy proficiency was linked to better use of e-journals, e-books, and databases—critical for effective literature searches. However, At the University of Eswatini, Nyathi and Ngwenya (2025) reported relatively high of awareness and moderate utilization among undergraduates, noting gaps in awareness that warrant library-led instructional campaigns .

Overall, studies consistently identify e-journals, e-books, online databases, and institutional repositories as the most used electronic information resources, while connectivity issues, inadequate infrastructure, and limited ICT skills continue to impair full adoption (Buba & Lawal, 2023; Mabawonku et al., 2023; Nyathi & Ngwenya, 2025). The literature underscores that, while electronic information resources offer many benefits such as remote access, currency, searchability, and multimedia features, they also demand sufficient ICT infrastructure and digital literacy (Mabawonku et al., 2023; Rivers State study, 2024) . These findings reinforce earlier claims by Liew et al. (2000) and Brophy (1993) that electronic formats bring advanced functionality (search, saving, remote access), but require new user competencies.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted was descriptive survey research, using quantitative method to collect data because it is a suitable and efficient way of studying large populations. The population of this study covered all ND and HND, a proportionate random sampling was used to represent the entire population which is one of the probability sampling techniques, to ensure proportional representative in the sample size, Research Advisor’s table (2006) was use to recruit 200 participants using krejcie and Morgan formula. A personally developed Questionnaire using three (3) points likert scale technique was used as an instrument for data collection which were administered personally by the researchers. The data collected was analyze using descriptive statistics where frequency tables, percentages, means and standard deviation were used to present and analyze the data.

4.0 RESULT

The chapter presented, analyzed, and interpreted the data obtained from the questionnaire administered to the respondents to answer the research questions of the study. The data were then summarized in tables showing frequencies and percentages for each item. Responses were evaluated based on a midpoint average of 2.0, where a score below 2.0 indicated agreement, and a score above 2.0 indicated disagreement. Additionally, the standard deviation was used to assess the consistency of the responses; a low standard deviation indicated that the responses were close to the mean, while a high standard deviation suggested greater variability. The use of both mean and standard deviation helped to confirm whether the results reflected agreement or disagreement among the respondents.

Table 1. Response Rate

Name of Polytechnic	No. of Quest. Distributed	No. of Quest. Returned	%
ND Students	97	91	43.3
HND Students	103	103	49.0
Total	200	194	92.3

The data in Table 1 Shows the response rates of two categories of students in the polytechnic under study (ND and HND Students of Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic Kazaure Jigawa state), based on the number of questionnaires distributed and returned. The researcher distributed 97 questionnaires and received 91 back from ND Students, resulting in a response rate of 43.3%. likewise 103 questionnaires was distributed to HND Students and received 103, yielding a higher response rate of 49%. The combined response rate for both students was 92.3%, with a total of 200 questionnaires distributed and 194 returned. This indicates a generally high level of engagement from all the students.

Table 2. Demographic Data of the Respondents

Items	HND Students			ND Students	
		F	%	F	%
Gender	Male	75	73	59	65
	Female	28	27	32	35

Table 2 presents the demographic data on question regarding the gender of the respondents. For HND Students 75 respondents (72.8%) were male, and 28 respondents (27.2%) were female. In contrast, 59 (65%) respondents of the respondents for ND Students were male, while 32 respondents (35.2%) were female. This indicates that all the students had a higher proportion of male respondents, but the gender distribution for ND Students was more balanced compared to HND Students

Table 3. Types of Electronic Information Resources currently available in the Polytechnic library under study?

Items	HND Students								ND Students							
	A		D		NS		MEAN	STD	A		D		NS		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%	F	%		
E-book	60	58.3	18	17.5	25	24.3	1.66	.85	65	71.4	12	13.2	14	15.4	1.44	.75
Offline Databases	88	85.4	8	7.8	7	6.8	1.21	.55	84	92.3	3	3.3	4	4.4	1.12	.44
E-mail	63	61.2	24	23.3	16	15.5	1.54	.75	28	30.8	52	57.1	10	11.0	2.14	.32
Online database	38	36.9	41	39.8	24	23.3	1.86	.77	39	42.9	42	46.2	10	11.0	1.68	.66
Internet services	54	52.4	26	25.2	23	22.3	1.70	.81	62	68.1	18	19.8	11	12.1	1.44	.70
Catalogue (OPAC)	34	33.0	51	49.5	18	17.5	1.84	.70	15	16.5	69	75.8	7	7.7	1.91	.49
CD - ROM	26	25.2	45	43.7	32	31.1	2.06	.75	10	11.0	69	75.8	12	13.2	2.02	.49
E-Journals	48	46.6	28	27.2	27	26.2	1.80	.83	25	27.5	41	45.0	25	27.5	2.00	.75

Table 3 shows the data in response to Research Question 1, regarding the types of electronic information resources available in the polytechnic library under study, as indicated in the table there is a general trend of agreement on the availability of various resources, with mean deviation values mostly below 2.0, indicating agreement. Specifically, e-books and offline databases, were considered available bases on the responses received from both HND and ND Students ranging from 1.44 to 1.66. Similarly, internet services, Email and online databases had mean values indicating agreement (1.44 to 1.86). However, OPAC, e-journal and CD-ROM had mean values slightly above 2.0, especially the responses received from the ND students, suggesting mixed or less clear perceptions of availability. Based on the finding of this research it implies that polytechnic libraries should focus on improving the availability and accessibility of resources like OPAC and CD-ROMs to meet users' needs.

Table 4. Extent of Utilization of Electronic Resources

Items	HND Students								ND Students							
	O		R		N		MEAN	STD	O		R		N		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%	F	%		
E-book	87	79.1	8	7.8	8	7.8	1.23	.58	63	69.2	18	19.8	10	11.0	1.42	.68
Offline Databases	95	92.2	5	4.9	3	2.9	1.11	.39	79	86.8	9	9.9	3	3.3	1.16	.45
Email	55	51.5	36	35.0	14	13.6	1.62	.72	36	39.6	44	48.4	11	12.1	1.73	.67
Online database	38	36.9	41	39.8	24	23.3	1.86	.77	39	42.9	42	46.2	10	11.0	1.68	.66
Internet services	54	52.4	26	25.2	23	22.3	1.70	.81	62	68.1	18	19.8	11	12.1	1.44	.70
Catalogue (OPAC)	34	33.0	51	49.5	18	17.5	1.84	.70	15	16.5	69	75.8	7	7.7	1.91	.49
CD - ROM	26	25.2	45	43.7	32	31.1	2.06	.75	10	11.0	69	75.8	12	13.2	2.02	.49
E - Journal	48	46.6	28	27.2	27	26.2	1.80	.83	25	27.5	41	45.0	25	27.5	2.00	.75

Keys: O = often, R = Rarely, N = Never

Table 4, shows the findings from Research Question 5 which revealed that students in the polytechnic utilize electronic information resources at different levels. E-books and other offline databases were the most frequently utilized resources, with high percentages of students reporting usage of 79.1% and 92.2% for HND Students with a Mean of 1.23 & 1.11, while 69.2% and 86.8% for ND Students with a Mean 1.42 & 1.16. In contrast, resources like e-journals and online databases were utilized less frequently, with a higher percentage of respondents indicating they do not use these resources. The mean values for usage were generally low for less frequently accessed resources, indicating lower levels of engagement with these types of electronic resources. The findings indicated that while students are actively utilizing key electronic resources like e-books and offline databases, there is a lower engagement with other resources such as OPAC and CD ROM. This indicates that certain resources may not be fully integrated into the research and learning practices, potentially limiting the overall utilization of the library's electronic offerings.

Table 5. Frequency of usage of Electronic Information Resources

Items	HND Students								ND Students							
	A		D		NS		MEAN	STD	A		D		NS		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%	F	%		
Often	68	66.0	22	21.4	13	12.6	1.46	.71	61	67.0	25	27.5	5	5.5	1.38	.59
Weekly	57	55.3	28	27.2	18	17.5	1.62	.77	45	49.5	31	34.1	15	16.5	1.67	.75
Bi- weekly	72	69.9	0	0	31	30.1	1.60	.92	65	71.4	20	22.0	6	6.6	1.35	.60
Rarely	35	34.0	53	51.5	15	14.6	1.81	.67	31	34.1	45	49.5	15	16.5	2.03	2.2

Table 5 Shows the findings from Research Question 3 indicate that students primarily utilize electronic information resources frequently, respond received from HND Students indicated that they utilize electronic resources often and bi-weekly with mean values reflecting strong agreement (1.38 to 1.60). while some among them shows that they utilize the resources weekly which also played a significant role, with mean values of 1.62 for HND Students and 1.67 for ND Students. On the other hand, access rarely with mean values above 2.0, indicating disagreement or less frequent use the resources.

Table 6. Benefit derived from utilization of Electronic Information Resources

Items	HND				ND Students			
	Yes		No		Yes		No	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
High	27	26.2	76	74.5	24	26.4	67	73.6
Moderate	62	60.2	41	39.8	56	61.5	35	38.5
Slightly	10	9.7	93	90.3	10	11.0	81	89.0

Table 6 The findings from Research Question 4 show that the majority of the students benefit moderately from utilization of electronic information resources. For HND, 60.2% of students reported having moderate benefit, while 26.2% highly benefited from the resources. Similarly, for ND Students, 61.5%, indicated moderate benefit from utilization of electronic information resources and 26.4% indicated high benefit. A smaller percentage of students reported that their benefit is low, with 9.7% for HND Students and 11.0% for ND. The findings shows that majority of students in the polytechnic have benefited moderately from utilization of electronic information resources.

Table 7. Purpose of Utilization of Electronic Information Resources.

Items	HND. Students								ND Students							
	A		D		NS		MEAN	STD	A		D		NS		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%	F	%		
Personal Use	24	23.3	55	53.4	24	23.3	2.00	.69	41	45.1	35	38.5	15	16.5	1.71	.73
Assignment/Project	86	83.5	6	5.8	11	10.7	1.27	.64	85	93.4	4	4.4	2	2.2	1.09	.35
Research purpose	32	31.1	22	21.4	49	47.6	2.17	.88	38	41.8	21	23.1	32	35.2	1.93	.88
Academic purpose	72	69.9	13	12.6	18	17.5	1.47	.78	65	71.4	12	13.2	14	15.4	1.44	.75
Online registration	79	76.7	10	9.7	14	9.7	1.37	.71	56	61.5	16	17.6	19	20.9	1.59	.82
Communication with friends	28	27.2	39	37.9	36	35.0	2.08	.79	18	19.8	45	49.5	28	30.8	2.11	.71

Table 7 Contain data from Research Question 5 which reveals that students access electronic information resources with varying purposes. For HND Students, the highest purpose of EIR utilization is assignment/projects with a (mean = 1.27) and research purpose (mean = 1.37). Similarly, For ND Students, purpose of utilization was also through writing assignment/project (mean = 1.09), followed by academic purposes (mean = 1.44). However, sources personal use, Online registration, and communication with friends showed a higher degree of disagreement, with mean values above 2.0. This indicated that students utilize electronic information resources for the purposes of their academic activities.

Table 8: Challenges associated with Utilization of Electronic Information Resources

Items	HND Students								ND Students							
	A		D		NS		MEAN	STD	A		D		NS		MEAN	STD
	F	%	F	%	F	%			F	%	F	%	F	%		
Inadequate power supply	81	78.6	7	6.8	15	14.6	1.36	.73	73	80.2	17	17.6	2	2.2	1.22	.47
Inability to access the available electronic database	55	51.5	36	35.0	14	13.6	1.62	.72	36	39.6	44	48.4	11	12.1	1.73	.67
Inadequate ICT skills	23	22.3	72	69.9	8	7.8	1.85	.53	10	11.0	51	56.0	30	33.0	2.22	.63
Too much of information	57	55.3	28	27.2	18	17.5	1.62	.77	45	49.5	31	34.1	15	16.5	1.67	.75
Distraction from other work	15	14.7	80	77.7	8	7.8	1.85	.53	10	11.0	51	56.0	30	33.0	2.22	.63
Limited access to computer terminals	34	33.0	51	49.5	18	17.5	1.84	.70	15	16.5	69	75.8	7	7.7	1.91	.49
Erratic power supply	72	69.9	0	0	31	30.1	1.60	.92	65	71.4	20	22.0	6	6.6	1.35	.60
Poor internet connectivity	95	92.2	5	4.9	3	2.9	1.11	.39	79	86.8	9	9.9	3	3.3	1.16	.45
Time consuming	26	25.2	45	43.7	32	31.1	2.06	.75	10	11.0	69	75.8	12	13.2	2.02	.49
Time frame	23	22.3	72	69.9	8	7.8	1.85	.53	10	11.0	51	56.0	30	33.0	2.22	.63

Table 8 revealed that several challenges face students in utilizing electronic information resources. Common issues included poor internet connectivity (mean = 1.36 for HND Students and 1.22 for ND Students), inadequate power supply (mean = 1.11 for HND Students and 1.16 at ND Students), and erratic power supply (mean = 1.60 for HND Students Poly and 1.35 for ND Students) were significant barriers for all students. Additionally, too much of information and inability to access available electronic databases (mean = 1.62 for HND Students and 1.73 for ND Students), lack of ICT skills (mean = 1.85 for HND Students and 2.22 for ND. Students), and distraction from other work (mean = 1.85 for HND Students Poly and 2.22 for ND Students) were also highlighted. The limited access to computer terminals and time consuming were less frequently mentioned, but still contributed to challenges in resource utilization (mean = 1.84 for HND Students and 1.91 for ND Students; mean = 2.06 for HND Students and 2.02 for ND Students). The findings shows that students utilization to electronic information resources is hindered by significant infrastructural challenges, such as poor internet connectivity and erratic power

supply, which affect the overall effectiveness of library services. Furthermore, skill gaps and limited access to computer terminals highlight the need for ongoing training and improved communication to ensure that students can fully utilize available resources.

5. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the factors affecting the utilization of electronic information resources (EIRs) by students at Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic, Kazaure, Jigawa State. The research specifically explored the availability of these resources, their extent and frequency of use, the perceived benefits, the purposes for which they are utilized, and the challenges encountered during usage.

The findings indicate that although electronic information resources such as e-books, databases, and internet services are available within the institution's library, their utilization by students remains suboptimal. E-books, databases, and internet services emerged as the most frequently accessed resources, primarily for academic purposes such as completing assignments, conducting research, and other scholarly activities. Despite the moderate benefits reported by the students, their usage patterns revealed a tendency to access these resources on a bi-weekly basis.

Several barriers to effective utilization were identified, including poor internet connectivity, unstable electricity supply, information overload, and limited access to available resources. These challenges significantly hinder students from fully benefiting from the electronic resources provided.

In light of these challenges, it is recommended that the polytechnic administration prioritize investment in information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure, enhance internet connectivity, and organize regular training sessions aimed at building students' information literacy skills. Additionally, awareness campaigns should be conducted to promote the availability and advantages of electronic information resources.

Addressing these constraints is essential for improving the accessibility and effective use of electronic information resources. Doing so will contribute to enhancing the quality of teaching, learning, and research not only in Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic but also across other institutions in North-West Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to address the identified issues and improve the access and utilization of electronic information resources in the polytechnic libraries:

1. Polytechnic management and the library administrators should enhance Resource Availability by Increasing the visibility and integration of underutilized resources like e-journals, OPAC and CD- ROMs e.t.c to make them more utilize.
2. Polytechnic management and the library management should upgrade internet infrastructures to provide faster and more reliable connectivity for accessing online databases
3. Polytechnic management and library management should implement ICT Training Programs by Providing targeted ICT training, specifically for the students to improve their proficiency in utilizing electronic resources.
4. The concern authorities should address infrastructure issues and other identified challenges through improve technological infrastructure by focusing on internet connectivity, reliable power supply, and securing funds to overcome existing barriers.
5. Government & Educational Regulators should develop policies that integrate electronic resources into polytechnic education, fund ICT development, and support partnerships with international digital libraries.

These steps will help improve the accessibility, utilization, and effectiveness of electronic information resources in polytechnic libraries.

Suggestions for Further Research

The study suggested the following areas for further studies:

- 1. Exploring Strategies to Enhance ICT Skills among Academic Staff:** This could include investigating the effectiveness of various training programs, workshops, and peer mentoring approaches, and how they contribute to better utilization of electronic resource
- 2. Examining the Relationship between Infrastructure Challenges and Resource Utilization**
- 3. Comprehensive comparative studies** focusing on the differences in electronic information resource usage between polytechnics and universities

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